

RISK ANALYSIS IN DOCUMENTARY LETTER OF CREDIT OPERATION

Abdusalomov Raxmonkul Erkinovich

ORCID iD: 0009-0007-7449-6458

Mail: raxmonkul.abdusalomov.707mail@mail.ru

*JSC «Aloqabank» Head Office, International Economic Relations Department,
Head of the Foreign Trade Financing and Documentary Operations division*

Abstract. *Documentary Letters of Credit are among most popular methods of payment used in international trade. They function as an irrevocable promise of issuing a bank to pay instead of an applicant buyer to a beneficiary seller under the condition that the beneficiary presents complying documents with terms and conditions of the credit to the bank. One of the reasons for the popularity of the LCs in international trade is shifting the payment risk from an individual buyer to a bank with a much stronger financial standing. However, LC operation in international trade is not free of risk. Despite the fact that two main principles of the Documentary Letter of Credit's Operation (Principle of independence and principle of strict compliance) facilitate the process of international trade significantly, but still all parties involved in LC operation are supposed to be cautious about the existing risks relevant to their role in LC operation. Current paper tries to use legal principles of documentary credits and risk management theory in order to define existing risks to each party (beneficiary, applicant and bank) in international LC transaction and find an answer to the question of what are exposing risks for involved parties? For this purpose, the paper starts with an explanation of the two main principles of LC operation and moves forward with using the risk management theory to explain existing risks for each party in detail.*

Key words: *International trade, Trade finance, Global financial crisis, Documentary Letter of Credits, Risk Analysis, Applicant, Beneficiary, Bank.*

Introduction.

Documentary Letters of Credit have long history in international trade. However, their legal nature goes back to the eighteenth century. In the course of international trade, when two businessmen from different parts of the world decide to have a transaction with each other, in addition to other methods of payment, LC can help them a lot in the realization of their deal by guaranteeing the payment to the seller by a bank, whereas the buyer also receives a guarantee that according to the presented documents by the beneficiary to the bank, he will receive purchased goods in accordance with the conditions stipulated in the underlying contract of sales. Such operation is regulated in the Uniform Customs and Practices for Documentary Letters of Credits (currently UCP

600) which is a set of norms defined for regulation of international LC transaction introduced by the International Chamber of Commerce for the purpose of protecting the flow of international trade and safeguarding the operation of Documentary Letters of Credits. It is subjected to two main principles of Strict Compliance and Autonomy. However, LC transaction is not a risk free operation and the current paper will try to use risk management theory to find an answer to the question of what are the main attributed risks to each party in LC operation. Preventing associated risks to each party in LC transaction can save huge amounts of money for each party and save the reputation of Documentary Letters of Credit as an effective and safe method of payment in international trade.

The Principle of Strict Compliance. The principle of Strict Compliance express that issuing a bank's undertaking to honour the credit is effective only upon presentation of complying documents by the beneficiary which are stipulated in the credit². On the other hand, "the idea of strict compliance has developed from the general principle of the law of agency that an agent is only entitled to reimbursement from his principal if he acts in accordance with his instructions"³. Therefore, banks who act as an agent for applicant in documentary credits will receive reimbursement in case of honouring the credit against complying documents. The standard for examination of documents has been set in Article 14 of UCP 600: "Article 14 Standard for Examination of Documents

a. A nominated bank acting on its nomination, a confirming bank, if any, and the issuing bank must examine a presentation to determine, on the basis of the documents alone, whether or not the documents appear on their face to constitute a complying Presentation.

d. Data in a document, when read in context with the credit, the document itself and international standard banking practice, need not be identical to, but must not conflict with, data in that document, any other stipulated document or the credit". The majority of discrepancies in practice of Documentary Letters of Credit include inconsistent data, discrepant documents of transport, mistakes in draft⁶, drafts without signature and inconsistent invoice with credit, inadequate insurance, and documents with wrong signature. In reality, principle of Strict Compliance is protecting interests of applicant under documentary credits process which requires shipment of promised goods by beneficiary before actualization of payment. about what constitutes the complying presentation which can be traced into legal cases. However, the most important question can be what is the characteristic of non-complying presentation? There are two main theories regarding the determination of documentary compliance: Doctrine of Strict Compliance and Doctrine of Substantial Compliance.

Doctrine of Strict Compliance. According to the doctrine of Strict Compliance, presented documents should strictly comply with credit. While former version of UCP (500) was requiring a bank to take a “Reasonable Care” in the process of examining compliance of presented documents by the beneficiary, UCP 600 has deleted such term which shows that only strict compliance is the criteria for reimbursement of a bank by the applicant. However, word by word compliance is not required by UCP 600. Simple mistakes and typographic errors might not be considered as non-conformity during the examination of documents and banks are unlikely to reject documents with minor defects. According to Woods, UCP 600 does not use the term of Strict and also provides permission for insignificant inconsistencies or errors. However, it is difficult to distinguish the insignificant error from the significant one. For example in *Seaconsar Far East Ltd v. Bank Markazi Jomhuri Islami Iran*, the credit defining all documents should bear the credit number and buyer’s name. However, one of the tendered documents missed the buyer’s name and the credit number. The Lloyd LJ held that the bank was entitled to reject the presentation: „[The plaintiffs] argues that the absence of the letter of credit number and the buyer's name was an entirely trivial feature of the document. I do not agree. I cannot regard as trivial something which, whatever may be the reason, the credit specifically requires. It would not help, I think, to attempt to define the sort of discrepancy which can properly be regarded as trivial.”

Therefore, discrepancies can be further divided into two main groups: Irrelevant Irregularities with no effect on principle of strict compliance and Material or Genuine discrepancies which violate the principle of strict compliance and result in rejection of documents by a bank.

Irrelevant Irregularities. Except for the case of Commercial Invoice, UCP 600 does not require for strict compliance of any documents presented by a beneficiary with terms and conditions of the Credit. In fact, some articles provide tolerance up to 10 percent regarding the amount or quantity of credit while terms like ‘about’ or ‘approximate’ are used in the credit. Other articles provide tolerance of 5 percent when quantity is not defined in the credit.

Material Discrepancy. There are numerous cases on material discrepancies. In *JH Raynor & Co. Ltd v. Hambro's Bank Ltd*, the shipped goods were described in the bill of lading as „machine-shelled ground kernels”, however, the credit had the description of goods as „Coromandel groundnuts”. In the judgement of the court of appeal, it was held that the bank was correct about rejection of tender despite the fact that the terms

were proved to be the same. As bank is not required to have the knowledge of the meaning of terms in different fields of trade. Other example is Courtaulds North America, Inc. v. North Carolina Nat. Bank in which the credit stipulated an invoice for '100% Acrylic Yarn' while the presented invoice described goods as 'Imported Acrylic Yarn'. The bank rejected the presentation. The court held that the bank was entitled to dishonour the presentation despite the fact that the description of goods on packing list were matching with the credit on the basis that UCP has differentiated the invoice from remaining documents. "Free of ineptness in wording the letter of credit dictated that each invoice express on its face that it covered 100% acrylic yarn. Nothing less is shown to be tolerated in the trade. No substitution and no equivalent, through interpretation or logic, will serve". Bank Melli Iran v. Barclays Bank (Dominion, Colonial & Overseas) is another important case on material discrepancies. In the above mentioned case the payment was due upon presentation of commercial invoice for shipment of '100 new Chevrolet trucks', while the invoice described goods as 'in new condition'. The court held that the bank was entitled to reject the presentation as 'in the new condition' and

'new' are not the same.

Substantial Compliance. It is the test accepted by few courts in order to balance the interests. The requirement of test is that the banker should "look beyond the face of the documents, investigate the realities of the transaction, and weigh the credibility of documents, customers and beneficiaries". Substantial Compliance has been considered in contradiction with Article 5 of UCP 600 which emphasizes on limitation of bank's responsibility to deal with documents not goods or services.

Principle of Autonomy. The second fundamental principle in operation of letters of credit is the Principle of Autonomy. This principle has been appreciated by national and international legal frameworks. The principle of autonomy of letters of credit has been considered as "cornerstone of the commercial validity of the letters of credit", and "the engine behind the letter of credit". The autonomy principle of letters of credit has been clearly mentioned in article 4 of UCP 600:

"Article 4 Credits v. Contracts

a. A credit by its nature is a separate transaction from the sale or other contract on which it may be based. Banks are in no way concerned with or bound by such contract, even if any reference whatsoever to it is included in the credit. Consequently, the undertaking of a bank to honour, to negotiate or to fulfil any other obligation under the credit is not subject to claims or defences by the applicant resulting from its relationships with the issuing bank or the beneficiary. A beneficiary can in no case avail itself of the contractual relationships existing between banks or between the applicant and the issuing bank.

b. An issuing bank should discourage any attempt by the applicant to include, as an integral part of the credit, copies of the underlying contract, proforma invoice and the like.”

Based on the Autonomy Principle and the text of article 4 of UCP 600, the beneficiary exporter has assurance that his payment will be due upon presentation of complying documents to the issuing bank while neither bank nor the account party can deny payment based on the arguments related to the performance of the underlying contract. Therefore, even in cases of argument on the performance of the underlying contract account party and the issuing bank have no other choice rather than paying the beneficiary upon presentation of complying documents and seek remedy by suing him for the breach of underlying contract. As a result, the Autonomy Principle has been considered a means of promoting international trade by following the logic of “pay first, argue later”. The autonomy principle also has been considered as the foundation for smooth operation of letter of credits by many scholars:

“We should also remember that in many international trade transactions, there are more parties involved than just the buyer or seller. The seller usually had to obtain goods or raw materials from a supplier before he is able to meet the contract made with the buyer. The seller will need to be financed in making payment to their suppliers. That financing comes from the negotiation or discounting of drafts drawn under the documentary credit system. Such system of financing would break down completely if the dispute between the seller and the buyer was to have the effect of „freezing” the sum in respect of which the letter of credit was opened”.

In order to completely address the essence of the autonomy principle, article 5 of UCP 600 specifies: “banks deal with documents and not with goods, services or performance to which the documents may relate”.

Risk Analysis. In the operation of Documentary Letters of Credits at least three parties will be involved. However, in accordance with complexity of the transaction, the number of parties and contracts among them will increase in practice. Main parties to LC transaction are the applicant, the beneficiary and the issuing bank but, advising bank, confirming bank, negotiation bank and reimbursing bank can be added to this list. Similar to all methods of payment in international trade each party in LC transaction is exposed to some level of uncertainty. The rest of the current paper will be dedicated to different types of the risk which can face either party in LC transaction.

Risks of the Applicant. The principal of independence in Documentary Letter of Credit operation facilitates the process of international trade by relying on the conformity of documents presented to the bank in order to honour the credit. However,

it can also raise the risk of fraud by providing ill-fated beneficiary the opportunity to present forged documents which are confirming with the terms of credit on their face without fulfilling his obligations in the underlying contract of sales. UNCITRAL report provides a list of four most common types of fraud which an applicant can face as a result of sole reliance of banks on strict compliance of documents presented by the beneficiary: The first one is falsification of documents by the beneficiary in order to obtain the payment from the issuing bank when no cargo exists in practice. The second is when delivered goods by the beneficiary do not comply with the contract of sales in quantity and quality. The third is selling the same cargo to more than one person and the fourth is issuing the document of title (bill of lading) twice for the same cargo. Additionally, banks have also been reported as frequent victims of fraud in LC transaction. *Sztejn v Henry Schroder Bank ing Corporation* is the legal case of LC transaction in which fraud was applied for the first time as the exception to the independence principle in LC operation. Despite the fact that the fraud rule is recolonized in different jurisdictions, still many courts prefer not to interfere in the autonomy of Documentary Letters of Credit which makes the applicant vulnerable to the risk of fraud. Interestingly, UCP 600 has taken an absolute silent position regarding the risk of fraud while leaving it open to national legal systems.

Risk of Inferior Quality and Quantity. Another risk which an applicant bears would be receiving goods with inferior quality and quantity instead of complying with the ordered quality in the international sales contract. Due to the documentary nature of LC transaction, in most cases, the applicant can have access to the document of title of ordered goods only after the negotiation of credit and receiving payment by the beneficiary. Therefore, there is a possibility for the beneficiary to ship the goods with inferior quality or quantity and negotiate the credit before the applicant has the access to the goods.

Risk of Issuing Bank's Negligence. Despite its very low probability, it is possible that the issuing bank relies on checking mechanisms of confirming and negotiating banks and releases problematic documents to the applicant without conducting due examination. As a result, the applicant faces with the risk of not receiving the release order from the carrier after presenting the forged or mistaken documents. On one hand, the bank has already honored or negotiated the credit and there is almost no possibility to retribute the money from the beneficiary and on the other hand, the applicant is unable to obtain the release order from the carrier because of non-complying documents.

Beneficiary's Risks. Despite the fact that terms and conditions of a credit should be in accordance with underlying contract, the buyer might neglect agreed terms in the contract of sales while opening the Letter of Credit or try to add new clauses in the

Credit and change the deal in his own favour. Most frequent situations are witnessed in case of price fluctuation and strict foreign currency control in destination markets that lead to late opening or not opening of the credit by the applicant. The applicant might also disregard the underlying contract of sales by inserting conditions in the Credit. For Example, the applicant changes the port of delivery, terms of delivery, type of insurance or includes other restrictive terms which are known as “Flexible Clauses”.

Risk of Documentary Discrepancy. The standard for examination of documents has been set in Article 14 of UCP 600: “Article 14 Standard for Examination of Documents

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As a result of the complex process and interactions between the bank and the traders in LC transaction, there is a high probability for occurrence of the documentary discrepancy. The risk of financial loss and dishonoring presentation by the bank will raise when there is no possibility to resolve discrepancies. Such discrepancy can be considered as a significant risk for the exporter as according to ICC the global rate of documentary discrepancy in LC transaction is about 60–70%. Documentary discrepancy rate in the USA is considered about 73% 64 while in the UK it has been estimated to have amounted up to 50–60%. Despite the fact that the costs of the documentary discrepancy have not been studied globally, but SITPRO study showed “that in 2000 the UK lost 113 million through non-compliant documents being presented under Letters of Credit”. As it was mentioned before, the majority of discrepancies in practice of Documentary Letters of Credit include inconsistent data, discrepant documents of transport, mistakes in drafts, drafts without signature and inconsistent invoice with the credit, inadequate insurance, and documents with wrong signature. Therefore, the beneficiary is strongly recommended to put in place necessary check and balance systems in order not to bear the financial burden of the documentary discrepancy in LC operation.

Risks for the Bank. The international trade finance because of its short term, self-liquidating and secured nature is less risky for banks than other types of financing operations. However, it does not mean that banks neglect relevant risks to international trade in general and LC operation in particular. Banking risks in international LC operation can be divided into two main groups of Marco and Transactional Risks. The

macro risks include external risks which affect the bank's role in LC operation like country risk and bank's risk. Due to many reasons such as economic and political stability, trade relations, rule of law and the existence of law enforcement institutions, countries are divided into different risk categories. In dealing with high-risk countries, banks either reduce the credit limit or imposes higher charges of issuing, confirming or negotiating LCs. On the other hand, not all involving banks in LC operation have the same financial and reputation weight. Therefore, banks should consider elements of defining creditworthiness of their counter parts in other countries in order to secure receiving payment by them.

In addition to macro risks, while being involved in international LC transaction, banks are exposed to related risks of security of transaction. LC transaction risks are of three types: firstly, financial status of the customer and his credit history which is relevant to the risk of not receiving reimbursement after making payment to the beneficiary. Secondly, the nature of the traded goods: the account party might go bankrupt as a result of high level of fluctuation in price of goods and as eventually it may be possible for the issuing bank not to receive reimbursement. Therefore, banks should consider the risk of issuing LC for commodities with highly volatile market. The third and final element of transitional risk is the bank's position and her relations with other involved banks in the international LC operation. The issuing bank faces major risks as it is recommended to check not only the creditworthiness of her own customer but also the credibility of the beneficiary and her bank as well . Exporter's bank also should check the reliability of issuing, confirming and negotiating banks overseas. There are occasions for fraud which can result in honoring LC by confirming the bank when the applicant does not accept the documents and the issuing bank does not effectuate the reimbursement accordingly. In such situation, the only solution for confirming the bank includes recourse clauses in her contract of negotiation with the beneficiary in order to prevent the risk of fraud.

Conclusion.

The importance of Documentary Letters of Credit as a method of payment in international trade which can balance conflicting interests of exporter and importer by transferring the payment risk from the importer to the issuing bank is constantly growing due to constant development in trade among nations. Despite the fact that the main objective of LC operation is to reduce the level of risk in the international trade, still all involved parties to international LC transaction face numerous types of risk which can create problems in smooth operation of trade between the importer applicant and the exporter beneficiary. Some risks even affect the banking operation involved in LC transaction. The current paper tried to shed light on different risks which either

party might face in the international LC transaction in order to warn them against the existence of such risks and prepare them to adapt proper risk management methods.

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